

**Proceedings of International
Multidisciplinary Scientific-
Remote Online Conference on
Innovative Solutions and
Advanced Experiments**

Organised by
**Samarkand Regional Center for
Retraining and Advanced Training
of Public Education Staff
Samarkand, Uzbekistan**

June 18th & 19th, 2020

In Association with
Novateur Publication India's

JournalNX

**A Multidisciplinary Peer
Reviewed Journal**
journalnx.com

ISSN: 2581-4230

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REFLECTION ISSUES OF NATIONAL ORIGINALITY IN THE TRANSLATION OF HISTORICAL NOVELS

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Annotation: The article gives an idea of the issues of the expression of national specific words in translation. Examples of the English translation of the novel by Abdulla Qadiri “Days gone by” are given.

Keywords: historical novel, national originality, translator, translation, reader, national literature.

It is known to all of us that the role of artistic literature in socio-cultural life, in the formation of mutual sympathy and warm relations between people is enormous. In addition, the role of literature in the spiritual enrichment of the inner world of every person, the rise of human qualities, the increase in literacy are incomparable. We can also see this in the decision of the president of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev “On the program of measures for the development of the system of publication and distribution of book products, on the program of measures for the promotion of reading and increasing the culture of reading” on September 13, 2017. Therefore, the involvement of young people in reading books at all times, the publication of artistic works that show our culture, spirituality and history is one of the urgent tasks of this day. [1, p4]

There are such works, no matter how long since they were written, they will never lose their fan, their readers, most importantly, their artistic significance. In fact, it's only about a century ago that Abdulla Qadiri's novel "Days gone by" is still coming in the hands of its readers. How this work conquered the hearts of readers of the last century, It is also so valuable for today's readers too. The translation of such Uzbek national masterpiece into foreign languages serves as one of the main means of recognition of our national literature to the world.

Translation is a powerful weapon that serves the interests of friendship, brotherhood and cooperation between peoples, as well as economic-political, scientific, cultural and literary ties between them.[2, p 113] Translated works give chance to readers to enjoy the masterpieces of World Literature, and their aesthetic feelings will increase, their tastes will grow, concepts about beautiful things will appear in them.

Each artistic work expresses the events that occur in a certain period of time. Therefore, a work created on a historical theme will acquaint the reader of the present time with the history of the life of the people. A distinctive feature of historical works is that such works contain a large number of historical and archaic linguistic means in accordance with the need of the period. Such tools not only animate the mood, landscape, breath of that period in the eyes of the readers, but also increase the artistic-aesthetic sensibility of the work. The responsibility to recreate the spirit of the original in a carefree manner puts before the translator the task of truthful interpretation of the spirit of the period when the work was created through the use of language tools.[2, p 113]

Until now, unfortunately, foreign readers were not sufficiently aware of Abdulla Qadiri's creative heritage. The translation of his historical novel “Days gone by” into English serves to introduce this great work to the world, through it the culture, customs and national peculiarities of the entire Uzbek people. The work shows not only the love between two people, but also various aspects of our social life: father and son, mother-in-law and daughter-in-law relations, kindness between people, kindness, as well as the tragic aspects of such vices as humiliation, malice, ignorance. That is why the responsibility of a full-fledged re-creation of the original mood in the process of translation of such historical novels requires the translator to recreate the

feature of the period in which the original was created by the correct selection of the necessary linguistic means.

As is known from history, as time goes by, some words become obsolete, new words appear in their place. Naturally, obsolete words will be unfamiliar to the reader of the present generation, and will bring for him various difficulties in understanding the work. In later editions of this work, serious attention was paid to these aspects, the meaning of Arabic, Persian, obsolete and difficult to understand terms and sentences, which were widely consumed in the period of writing the work, but now are incomprehensible to young readers, were given to young readers with explanations. [1, p 4]

In the English translation of the novel “Days gone by”, which is considered the first example of the Uzbek School of National Novel, which is one of such historical novels, a number of historical and archaic words and translations of national specific words are expressed in a special way.

This work was first translated into English with the support of the Karimov Foundation and published in the publishing house Nouveau Monde Editions in France in 2018. The translation of the novel was carried out by the British literary critic Carol Ermakova, who translated more than thirty fictions.

In the event that the novel “Days gone by” reflects historical events, we can see how some historical and archaic words, as well as words and expressions representing the national identity, are expressed in the English translation carried out by Carol Ermakova. As we hold the work in our hands, we can see that Abdulla Qadiri used a lot of national specific words in it. National specific words dedicated to the work the national spirit, the national and historical landscape of that period are seen before the eyes of the readers. It is possible to witness that in order to preserve both nationality and originality in the form of a translation, the translator Karol Ermakova left many words and phrases in its own way, or made a comment at the bottom of the page using historical words in English.

“Saroyning to’rida boshqalarg’a qarag’anda ko’rkamrak bir hujra, anovi hujralarga kiygiz to’shalgani holda bu hujrada qip-qizil gilam, uttalarda bo’z ko’rpalar ko’rilgan bo’lsa, munda ipak va adras ko’rpalar, narigilarda qora chiroq sasiganda, bu hujrada sham yonadur,”...[1, p 6]

English translation:

“In the far reaches of the courtyard we see a snug room, marked by the elegance of its décor. If simple koshma felt rugs cover the floors in other rooms, here we find rich crimson carpets; if coarse blankets festoon the other quarters, here they are replaced by kurpach covers made of silks and adrases; if oil lamps smoke in other rooms, here candle flames flicker in a lively dance.” [3, p 7]

The translator also saved the national originality in the form of a translation by commenting on the words Kurpach and adras at the bottom of the page as follows.

“Kurpach- a traditional quilted mattress stuffed with felt or soft cotton generally covered in silk or cotton, used not only on beds but also in seating areas”.

“Adras- striped or monotone semi-silk fabrics with colourful designs”. [3, p 8]

“— Bizni kechirasiz, bek aka, — deb Raxmat uzr ayt-di, — vaqtsiz kelib sizni tinchsizladik.” [1, p 7]

English translation:

“Forgive us bek aka,” Rakhmat began, “for disturbing you with a visit at this untimely hour.” [3, p 8]

Here are the comments given below to Bek and aka.

“Bek- Ruler and leader; in this case, it is used as a polite and respectful form of address, akin to lord.”

“Aka- lit. ‘uncle’ commonly used as a term of respect when addressing one’s elders.” [3, p 8]

But in the first lines of the work we can see such words that they do not reflect national originality in English translations.

“1264-inchi hijriy, dalv oyining oʻn yettinchisi, qishki kunlarning biri, quyosh botqan, tevarakdan **shom azoni** eshitaladir”.

English translation:

“It was seventeenth day of the month of dalv, hijri year 264. A wintry day. Calls to **evening prayer rang** from all around as the sun set...”

Here, as a translation of the word shom azoni is given in rang in English translation, and the translation of this word is not reflected correctly in the word rang. If the explanation of this word had been given, it would have been possible to see our national originality in the eyes of the English readers in the same way as it was in the original.

Translation will not be without defects. It is natural for such small defects to occur. But anyway, it is a pleasure for the people of the world to enjoy our national works.

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